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Deconstructing mythologemes of totalitarian society in Ukrainian musicology

The revival of Ukrainian culture and its full entry into the circle of European cultures requires in-depth research and filtering of the “alien” that came to Ukraine as a result of long colonial enslavement. For many centuries, Russia, and later the Soviet Union, pursued a colonial cultural policy of aggression based on an extensive system of methods aimed at appropriating Ukrainian cultural and artistic artifacts, destroying Ukrainian cultural identity, erasing the national memory of the most important events of the Ukrainian national liberation movement, etc.

One of the most effective methods of ideological struggle against Ukrainians in the field of musical art was the construction and forced imposition of artificial narratives and mythologemes both within the former Soviet Union and abroad that discredited the value and independence of Ukrainian art and its ability to produce works of high artistic value. The purpose of this article is to deconstruct at least some of these totalitarian narratives and to correct perceptions of the ways in which Ukrainian music has developed, its role and place in the European and world cultural heritage.

First of all, it should be noted that the formation of Soviet ideological postulates about the inferiority of Ukrainian culture took place in different places and in different ways. Cultural and mass media platforms of various levels were used to implement targeted anti-Ukrainian ideological policy, from educational courses for schoolchildren and students and lectures for workers and laborers to radio and television programs. Particular attention was paid to publishing, because due to the mass nature of textbooks, books, brochures and samples of other printed materials, the ideas needed by the ruling elite were quickly and widely spread in society.

Our attention was drawn to popular science and educational publications of the 1960s-1980s, in particular the brochure *Musical Ukraine*.¹ The purpose of this publication was to familiarize Soviet and foreign readers with the trends in the development of Ukrainian musical art in the 1980s, the activities of leading musical groups and educational institutions, and the works of prominent Ukrainian composers. In practice, the supposedly noble goal of popularizing Ukrainian musical art was combined with ideological anti-Ukrainian narratives that had been present in Russian cultural policy since imperial times.

¹ *Ukraina myzyczna [Musical Ukraine]*, Kyiv: URO VAAP, 1983. 108 p.

The main narrative that was widely used in Soviet and Ukrainian musicology is *the myth of the unity of Ukrainian and Russian cultures, the commonality of their roots and sources, and, accordingly, the antiquity of Russian culture*. Today, in the times of the Russian-Ukrainian war, this myth is one of the cornerstones of the idea of the “Russian world.” This mythologeme is fed by the achievements of Ukrainian culture appropriated by Russia. An example of such imperial thinking can be found in Tatiana Zolozova's article *Berezovsky's Sonata*, where in the very first sentence we read: “The Sonata for Violin and Cembalo by Maksym Sozontovych Berezovsky, a classic of eighteenth-century Ukrainian and Russian music, was recently discovered in France.”² Maksym Berezovsky is not a classic of Russian music, no matter how much the ideologues of the “Russian world” would like to claim that he is. As you know, the forced deportation of talented Ukrainian children to the court singing chapel in St. Petersburg was a common practice for the cultural “managers” of the imperial court in the eighteenth century. This is how Maksym Berezovsky, Dmytro Bortniansky, Semen Hulak-Artemovsky, Fedir Yakymenko, and dozens of other talented Ukrainian boys singers ended up in the northern Russian capital at a very young age. No one asked these children's opinions or their parents' permission to leave their homeland and serve the Russian emperor by entertaining him with their beautiful singing. Moreover, a singing school was founded in the town of Hlukhiv in the Sumy region to select and train future singers for the court singing chapel. In this way, talented musicians were systematically “siphoned off” from Ukraine. Ukrainian young men often arrived in St. Petersburg as well-trained, well-formed musicians, and then they were sent abroad to improve their performing and composing skills, usually to Italy. In this way, talented Ukrainian boys became Russian singers and composers. However, they never forgot who they were and what kind of people they were. The nature of Ukrainian folk singing and the traditions of Orthodox choral culture became the basis for the *partes* choral concerts of Dmitro Bortniansky and Maxim Berezovsky.

In the above-mentioned article by T. Zolozova about M. Berezovsky's Sonata for Violin and Cembalo, we come across another terminological “invention” of Soviet ideology: “According to experts, this is the earliest example of large-form domestic music.”³ By using the adjective “domestic” in reference to a work of art, researchers often veiled or deliberately concealed the Ukrainian origin of an artifact or cultural phenomenon.

Today, Ukraine rightfully declares that the works of D. Bortniansky and M. Berezovsky belong unconditionally to the musical culture of the Ukrainian people. Both of these musicians were universal artists and had a great influence not only on

² Zolozova T., *Berezovsky's Sonata*, in: *Ukraina myzyczna [Musical Ukraine]*, Kyiv: URO VAAP, 1983, p. 66-67, here p. 66.

³ *Ibid*, p.67.

Ukrainian music, but also on the development of the entire European musical culture. According to Olha Shumilina, a researcher of Maksym Berezovsky's life and work, "M. Berezovsky was one of the first Ukrainian musicians whose work organically combined various branches of professional activity of a musician of the eighteenth century: church choirboy and opera singer, instrumentalist and chapel master, composer of secular and sacred music. Ukrainian musical culture has never known a person of such a level of talent and professional training before."⁴

The mythologeme of the inseparable unity of Ukrainian and Russian cultures was used even in cases where it was a question of purely Ukrainian national phenomena of culture and art. For example, in Olga Polianychko's article on musical Shevchenkiana, we read: "Since the middle of the nineteenth century, none of the Ukrainian composers have passed by the poetry of Taras Shevchenko. His fiery lines became the basis for numerous works by not only Ukrainian but also Russian authors. Mussorgsky and Lysenko, Tchaikovsky and Stetsenko, Rachmaninoff, Liudkevych, Stepovyi and many others wrote on Shevchenko's poems."⁵ It is surprising that in a short note on musical compositions to poems by the Ukrainian national poet Taras Shevchenko, the author could not do without mentioning Russian music, although for the Russian composers she noted, reference to Shevchenko's work is an exception rather than a rule. In O. Polianychko's text, subtle semantic accents shift the reader's attention from Ukrainian music to Russian music, and in the list of composers' names, Russian composers are always on the first place. The priority of Russian music in musicological texts put Ukrainian music in a subordinate position, assigned it a secondary role, and created the effect of its lack of independence, and inferiority.

A similar practice was used in other publications, most textbooks and manuals. For example, in the textbook for music colleges and conservatories *Essays on the History of Ukrainian Music*, which was widely used in the 1960s and 1980s, the idea of the inseparability of Ukrainian culture from Russian culture and, even more so, the impossibility of independent development of the Ukrainian cultural ethnos, is the main idea. On page 109 of this manual we read: "...the Ukrainian people have never lost their will to freedom, they have always had a desire to reunite with the fraternal Russian people, which was the only way to gain independence and preserve their language and culture."⁶ There are many similar statements in the textbook, and not a single chapter is complete without mentioning Russian music, its

⁴ Shumilina O., Composer Maksym Berezovsky: a review of lifetime documentary materials (to the 270th anniversary of his birth), in: *Ukrainian music*, 2015/4 (18), p. 77-84, here p.84.

⁵ Polianychko O., His immortal muse, in: *Ukraina myzyczna [Musical Ukraine]*, Kyiv: URO VAAP, 1983, p. 58-59, here p. 58.

⁶ Arkhimovych L., Karysheva T., Sheffer T., Schreier-Tkachenko O., *Narysy z istorii ukrains'koi muzyky [Essays on the History of Ukrainian Music]*, Part I, Kyiv: Mystetstvo, 1964, p.109.

influence on the development of Ukrainian musical culture, the inevitability of Ukraine's reunification with Russia, etc. Such a powerful introduction of the ideas of Russian-Ukrainian unity into public circulation looks like an ideological special task for the team of authors.

The concept of the unity of the musical cultures of the Russian, Ukrainian, and Belarusian peoples was popular in Soviet times.

The introduction to the aforementioned textbook, *Essays on the History of Ukrainian Music*, began with the words about the triumvirate of Russian, Ukrainian, and Belarusian cultures: "The oldest source of Ukrainian music is the ancient culture of the ancient Eastern Slavs, which became the common basis for the musical art of the three fraternal peoples – Russian, Ukrainian and Belarusian."⁷ The same idea is emphasized in the last paragraph of the introduction: "The great cultural achievements of the times of Kievan Rus after its collapse became the basis for the emergence and development of art, literature, and music of the three fraternal East Slavic peoples, including Ukrainian musical culture."⁸

The postulate of the unity of the three fraternal peoples is the central theme of Professor Ivan Liashenko's article, in which we read: "The historical roots of this unity go back centuries, to the culture of Kievan Rus, which gave... the opportunity to mature and grow to Ukraine, Belarus, and Great Russia."⁹ First of all, it should be noted that Ivan Liashenko was a great patriot of Ukraine, an adherent of a broad European view of Ukrainian culture, and it was he who came up with the idea of creating the Center for Music Ukrainian Studies at the Kyiv Conservatory (now the National Music Academy of Ukraine), which would study European influences in Ukrainian musical culture and vice versa – the influence of Ukrainian music on European and world cultural processes. At the same time, Ivan Liashenko defended the concept of deep ties between the three national musical cultures (Russian, Ukrainian, and Belarusian), which were allegedly laid down in folk song. The researcher mistakenly believed that Ukrainian carols, shchedrivkas, vesniankas, haiivkas, obzhynkas, and samples of other genres of Ukrainian song folklore, as well as wedding and family songs, have their counterparts in Russian and Belarusian folk traditions.

However, ethnomusicological studies of the twenty-first century have argued and refuted the idea of the unity of Ukrainian, Belarusian, and Russian musical ethnic groups with solid evidence. In particular, based on the analysis of more than 60 thousand samples of folklore – Ukrainian, Russian, Belarusian and Lithuanian folk

⁷ Arkhimovych L., Karysheva T., Sheffer T., Schreier-Tkachenko O., *Narysyz istorii ukrains'koi muzyky [Essays on the History of Ukrainian Music]*, Part I, Kyiv: Mystetstvo, 1964. p. 6.

⁸ *Ibid.*, p. 12.

⁹ Liashenko I., Common powerful roots, in: *Ukraina myzyczna [Musical Ukraine]*, Kyiv: URO VAAP, 1983, p. 71-72, here p. 71.

songs – Iryna Klymenko compiled 132 melotypological maps, which allowed the researcher to identify similarities and differences in the traditional cultures of these peoples and to fix the geographical territory of the common melodic array. Klymenko writes: “The territorial core of the Slavic-Baltic Early Traditional melodic massif obtained by the total summary of the areas includes the entire ethnic spaces of Ukrainians and Belarusians, a large eastern Polish massif (the upper and middle parts of the Vistula basin), and the regions of southern Lithuania (Dzukia, Suvalkia)... On the segment of the Ukrainian-Russian linguistic demarcation, the line of the Slavic-Baltic early traditional melodic array moves eastward from the Ukrainian isogloss, joining several Russian-speaking districts of Briansk, Kursk, and Belgorod regions to the Slavic-Baltic early traditional melodic array.”¹⁰ Thus, I. Klymenko proved that Ukrainian folklore has common features with Belarusian, Polish, and Lithuanian folklore, but not with Russian folklore.

Ukrainian historians have further explored and debunked the imperial myth of the unity of the Russian, Ukrainian, and Belarusian “brotherly” peoples.

Volodymyr Bilinsky's study *The Country of Moksel or Moscovia*¹¹ collects facts from historical sources (mostly Russian) that testify to the radical distortion of the history of the Russian Empire, the distortion of historical truth, and the widespread narratives that Moscovia and Kyivan Rus have common historical roots and that Moscovia has “inheritance rights” to Kyivan Rus.

Bilinsky argues that during the existence of Kievan Rus there was no mention of the Moscow state.

From the ninth to twelfth centuries, the vast region from Tula, Riazan, and the present-day Moscow region was inhabited by the tribes of Merya, Ves', Moksha, Chud, Mordva, Mari, and others—all of them the Moksel people. These tribes later became the basis of the people who called themselves “Great Russians.” From the late thirteenth to the early eighteenth century, the people of this land were called Moscovites. To this day, Moscow historians remain silent on the question of their national origin.

In 1237, the Tatar Mongols came to the Suzdal land. All those who bowed their heads, kissed the khan's boots, and accepted his citizenship remained alive and unharmed; those who did not want to submit were killed. The Volodymyr princes Yurii Vsevolodovych and Yaroslav Vsevolodovych submitted to Batu Khan. Thus, the land of Moksel became part of the Golden Horde of the Genghis Khan's Empire. Genghis Khan's descendants ruled this land for over 270 years.

¹⁰ Klymenko I., Ritual melodies of Ukrainians in the context of the Slavic-Baltic early traditional melodic array: typology and geography: PhD thesis. 17.00.03 Musical Art. K.: NMAA, 2021, p. 26-27.

¹¹ Bilinsky V., *Kraina Moksel abo Moskovia [The Country of Moksel or Moscovia]*: in three books, Kyiv: Olena Teliha Publishing House, 2008/2009.

It is known that the Moscow principality as an ulus of the Golden Horde was founded by Khan Mengu-Timur only in 1277. By that time, Kievan Rus had already existed for over 300 years.

According to the research of Volodymyr Bilinsky, there is no evidence of the connection of Kievan Rus with the Finnish ethnic group of the Moksel land and later the Moscow principality with the principalities of the lands of Kievan Rus before the 16th century. At the time of the baptism of the state of Kievan Rus in 988, the Finnish tribes of the Moksel land were in a semi-wild state.

After the Genghis Khan dynasty was interrupted, the new Romanov (Kobylin) dynasty in 1613 pledged to keep the ancient traditions sacred and swore allegiance to the old Genghis Khan dynasty.

Thus, Moscovia is a direct heir to the Golden Horde, the state of the Genghisids, meaning that it was not the princes of Kievan Rus, but the Tatar-Mongols who were the “godfathers” of Moscow's statehood. The Moscow principality (and since 1547, the tsardom) had no ties to the principalities of the lands of Kievan Rus until the sixteenth century.

At the same time, the Moscow and later Russian tsars understood that without a great past it was impossible to create either a great nation or an empire. To do so, they had to embellish their historical past, invent it, or even steal someone else's history and culture. Therefore, the Moscow tsars, beginning with Ivan IV (the Terrible) (1533-1584), set their subjects the task of appropriating the history of Kievan Rus and its glorious past and, on its basis, creating the official mythology of the Russian Empire.

For many centuries, especially since the beginning of the sixteenth century, the myth has been spreading that the Russian state and the Russian people originated from the Grand Duchy of Kyiv; that Kyivan Rus was the cradle of three fraternal peoples – Russian, Ukrainian, and Belarusian – and that Russians, as “big brothers,” allegedly have the right to the heritage of Kyivan Rus.

The massive state falsification of the history of his people was carried out by Peter I. It was he who first issued a decree in 1701 to confiscate all written national monuments from the subjugated peoples: chronicles, chronographs, ancient historical records, church documents, archives, etc. This was especially true of Ukraine-Rus'. Peter the Great brought from Europe a large number of specialists, including professional historians, who were involved in writing and falsifying the history of the Russian state. They were all in the civil service, and one of the obligatory points of the agreement was their obligation to never leave the territory of Russia. In 1716, Peter the Great “made a copy” of the so-called Koenigsberg Chronicle, which allegedly recorded the “unification” of the ancient chronicles of the Kyiv and Moscow principalities and substantiated the unity of the Slavic and Finnish lands. However, access to the “copy”-fake, as well as to the original itself, was closed.

This Peter's falsification became the basis for further falsifications – the writing of the so-called “all-Russian chronicles”, which substantiated Moscovia's right to the succession of Kievan Rus. On the basis of these falsifications, on October 22, 1721, Moscovia declared itself the Russian Empire and Moscovites as Russians. This is how the historical name Rus was stolen from the rightful heirs of Kievan Rus – Ukrainians.

Empress Catherine II (1762-1796) continued this work on an even larger scale. Having familiarized herself with archival sources, Catherine II drew attention to the fact that the entire history of the state was based on verbal epic mythology and had no evidence base. Therefore, Catherine II, by her decree of December 4, 1783, created a “Commission for the compilation of notes on the ancient history of mainly Russia” under the direction and supervision of Count A. Shuvalov. The commission consisted of 10 prominent historians of the time. The main task that the empress set for the commission was to substantiate the “legitimacy” of Moscovia's appropriation of the historical heritage of Kievan Rus by rewriting chronicles, writing new chronicle collections, and other falsifications, and to create a historical mythology of the Russian state. The commission worked for 10 years. In 1792, Catherine's History was published. The work of the commission was carried out in the following areas:

- collecting all written documents (chronicles, archives, etc.). This work had already been partially done by Peter I. The collection of materials was carried out not in Russia, but also in other countries – Poland, Turkey, etc;

- studying, falsifying, rewriting, classifying, or destroying authentic historical materials;

- writing new “all-Russian summaries” in the eighteenth century, which were presented as if they were written in the eleventh, thirteenth, and fourteenth centuries. In fact, at the time when East Slavic tribes (Polians, Derevians, Siverians, etc.), who were already Christians, lived on the Kyivan land, Finnish tribes (Muroma, Meria, Ves', Moksha, etc.), who were in a semi-wild state, lived in the “Moscow” land, and these tribes had nothing to do with Kievan Rus until the 16th century;

- Thousands of different false chronicles and chronicles were written to substantiate the unity of Kievan Rus and the Finnish tribes. All of these “documents” exist only in copies, not a single original exists.

All this, according to another Ukrainian historian, Yaroslav Dashkevych, points to “incredible falsification in terms of shamelessness and impudence in inventing the non-existent history of the Russian state.”¹²

In addition to falsifications and distortions of historical truth, the most commonly used myth in Soviet musicology was *the myth of the exclusive influence of*

¹² Dashkevych Yaroslav, *Yak Moskovia pryvlasnyla istoriiu Kyivs'koi Rusi [How Moscovia Appropriated the History of Kievan Rus]*. <https://universum.lviv.ua/journal/2011/6/dashk.htm>

the Russian school of composition on the formation of Ukrainian professional music. It was used not only by Russian but also by Ukrainian musicologists. In particular, musicologist Mykola Hordiichuk, in his article *Symphonic Music*, analyzing the works of the founders of Ukrainian Soviet symphonism, Borys Liatoshynsky and Levko Revutsky, emphasized that "...as students of the outstanding composer and teacher Reinhold Gliere, they perceived the advanced aesthetic principles of Russian classical music and transferred them to the Ukrainian national soil."¹³ Mykola Hordiichuk went on to note the influence of Russian composers such as Piotr Tchaikovsky, Alexander Glazunov, Alexander Borodin, and Alexander Scriabin in the first symphonies of B. Liatoshynsky and L. Revutsky. But was it really only Russian music that guided the early works of Liatoshynsky and Revutsky? The tendency of M. Hordiichuk's approach is obvious. In the works of L. Revutsky, the influences of not Russian, but rather the centuries-old Ukrainian national song and choral tradition, which was reinterpreted in their works by Dmytro Bortniansky, Maksym Berezovsky, Artemii Vedel, Semen Hulak-Artemovskyy, Mykola Lysenko, Mykola Leontovych, and other composers, are clearly visible. By the way, in the work of Mykola Lysenko, who studied at the Leipzig Conservatory, European influences became very noticeable. L. Revutsky's studies at Mykola Lysenko's music and drama school and his direct communication with the founder of the Ukrainian professional composing school contributed to the implementation of European musical values in L. Revutsky's artistic and ideological system. As for B. Liatoshynskyy, it is known that his favorite composers were the Romantics Schubert, Liszt, and Wagner. In the early period of his career, Liatoshynsky was also interested in musical modernism, in particular symbolism, expressionism, and music by composers of the New Viennese school, and he highly appreciated Alban Berg's opera *Wozzeck*. Liatoshynsky was one of the first composers in the former Soviet Union to use atonality, for which he was later severely criticized and accused of so-called formalism by official musical circles. Thus, in our opinion, for the sake of objectivity, it is worth noting European, rather than Russian, influences in the works of Revutsky and Liatoshynsky.

It is impossible to ignore *the mythologeme of the Soviet ideological system about the decisive influence of the October 1917 revolution on the development of musical art*, including Ukrainian music. The hyperbolization of the role of the October Revolution of 1917¹⁴ in the life of Ukrainian society went hand in hand with the falsification of historical facts. One such falsification is found in an article about the State (now National) Academic Choir of Ukraine *Dumka*: "Born on the wave of

¹³ Gordeichuk N., Simfonicheskaya muzyka. Razvivaya bogatyie tradicii klassiki [Symphonic music. Developing the rich tradition of classics], in: *Ukraina myzyczna [Musical Ukraine]*, Kyiv: URO VAAP, 1983, p. 10-13, here p. 11.

¹⁴ In Soviet historiography, this event was called the Great October Socialist Revolution.

revolutionary enthusiasm in 1920, this first professional choir in Ukraine, which has gained wide recognition and popularity, draws its inspiration from the source of national music.”¹⁵ In addition to glorifying revolutionary sentiments, this phrase falsifies historical facts, in particular, changing the date of the founding of the *Dumka* Choir. In fact, the *Dumka* Choir was founded during the Ukrainian People's Republic in 1919. Since this event was close in time to the October 1917 upheaval, it was beneficial for Soviet ideologues to slightly “correct” the date of the choir's foundation, pushing it back a year to the time when the UPR had already ceased to exist. Of course, the real initiator and founder of *Dumka* (Ukrainian People's Republic) was not mentioned until the end of the Soviet era.

Thus, the analysis of popular science and educational publications about Ukrainian music published in the 1960s and 1980s shows a targeted Soviet cultural policy aimed at discrediting Ukrainian culture and art, trying to diminish the artistic value of Ukrainian cultural heritage, and creating the impression of its lack of independence and inferiority. The Russian-Ukrainian war, which has been going on for 10 years, has proved the absurdity of the mythologemes created by the ideologues of the Russian world. And right now, Ukraine has a historic chance to cleanse itself of centuries of lies, falsifications, and intellectual theft committed by its insidious northern neighbor, to restore historical justice and to reveal to the world its own version of the history of Ukrainian music.

¹⁵ Always original and talented, in: *Ukraina myzyczna [Musical Ukraine]*, Kyiv: URO VAAP, 1983, p. 63.